

D1.1

Project Management Plan (PMP) and Data Management Plan (DMP)

final release

skillbill

SKILL TO BOOST INNOVATION & PROFESSIONAL
FULFILLMENT IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

AzeroCO2

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	
1. OVERVIEW	7
1.1 Data Management Plan- general definition	7
1.2 Project Management Plan- general definition	8
1.3 Social, Ethical, Legal, Privacy issue- general definition	8
1.4 This document	8
2. PROJECT ABSTRACT	10
3. PROJECT PARTNERS	11
4. SKILLBILL DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN	12
4.1 Data Summary	12
4.1.1 Types, formats and origin of data	12
4.1.2 Re-use any existing data and how	13
4.1.3 Data utility	14
4.2 FAIR data principles	15
4.3 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	16
4.3.1 Metadata	16
4.3.2 File naming	17
4.3.3 Version File numbering.....	19
4.4 Making data accessible	20
4.5 Internal data collection.....	21
4.5.1 File storage	21
4.6 Making data interoperable	21
4.7 Increase data re-use	22
4.8 Other research outputs	22
4.9 Allocation of resources	22
4.10 Data security	23
5. SOCIAL, ETHICAL, LEGAL, PRIVACY ISSUE	25
5.1 Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislations	26
5.2 Gender equality	27
6. SKILLBILL PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN	28

- 6.1 Project Management general structure, roles and responsibilities 28**
 - 6.1.1 The Coordinator28
 - 6.1.2 The TCC.....29
 - 6.1.3 Advisory Board (AB)30
- 6.2 Project schedule 30**
- 6.3 Project budget..... 31**
- 6.4 Internal communication 31**
 - 6.4.1 Contact list.....31
 - 6.4.2 Meetings.....31
- 6.5 Project management tools 32**
 - 6.5.1 Template for monthly electronic update32
 - 6.5.2 Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)32
 - 6.5.3 Financial and Resource management33
- 7. ANNEX A: DATASET GENERATED BY THE PROJECT.....35**
- 8. ANNEX 1: MONTHLY UPDATE36**
- 9. ANNEX 2: WORK BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE (WBS).....37**
- 10. ANNEX 3: FINANCIAL AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT.....57**

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: screenshot of Dropbox repository for SKILLBILL 21
 Figure 2: screenshot of the file “Dataset” 35
 Figure 3: screenshot of the file “Monthly update “ 36
 Figure 4: screenshot of the file “Work Breakdown Structure“ 37
 Figure 5: screenshot of the file “Financial and Resource management“ 57

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: project partners with acronymous 11
 Table 2: project initial data utility 15
 Table 3: SKILLBILL list of deliverables 18

ABBREVIATIONS

AB	ADVISORY BOARD
CA	Consortium Agreement
CM	COMMUNICATION MANAGER
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identified
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OS	Open Science
PM	PROJECT MANAGER
PMP	Project Management Plan
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
TCC	TECHNICAL COORDINATION COMMITTEE
VET	Vocational Education and Training
WP	Work Package
WPL	WORK PACKAGE LEADERS

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides the final version of the SKILLBILL Data Management Plan and Project Management Plan; it is built on the initial version -submitted in Month 2 November 2022 and approved- to consider the actual procedures implemented throughout the project. Very few deviations were found compared to the original plan and they did not affect it in any way the smooth management of the project.

The deliverable outlines how the data collected or generated have been handled during the project. It describes which standards and methodology for data collection and generation have been followed, and whether and how the data is shared.

The procedures described below to protect data and ensure its quality will be applied by Partners even after the end of the project for all activities that will continue or be replicated (e.g. VET and Master courses).

This document has been drafted starting from the standard Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template¹. Additional information has been included.

1. Overview

1.1 Data Management Plan- general definition²

The Data Management Plan (DMPs) is a **key element** of good data management. A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the project; how the data have been and will be managed, described, and stored, what standards used, and how data handled and protected during and after the completion of the project.

As part of making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR), a **DMP includes information** on:

- the handling of data during & after the end of the project
- what data were collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology & standards are applied
- whether data are shared/made open access and

¹ <https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

- how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

1.2 Project Management Plan- general definition

The Project Management Plan (PMP) is the central document by which the project is formally managed. A Project Management Plan is a document which lists the activities, tasks and resources required to complete the project and to achieve the business benefits outlined in the Project description. A typical Project Plan includes:

- A description of the major phases undertaken to complete the project
- A schedule of the activities, tasks, durations, dependencies, resources and timeframes
- A listing of the assumptions and constraints identified during the planning process.

1.3 Social, Ethical, Legal, Privacy issue- general definition

Below the definition for the Social, Ethical, Legal, Privacy issue:

- Social issue is a problem that affects many people within a society¹
- Ethical issues involve rules or standards governing the conduct of members of a profession; ethical issues occur when a given decision, scenario or activity creates a conflict with a society's moral principles^{2, 3}.
- Legal issues involve rules governing the conduct of persons within a community, state, or country.
- Privacy is focused on the use and governance of personal data. Security focuses on protecting data from malicious attacks and the exploitation of stolen data for profit. While security is necessary for protecting data, it's not sufficient for addressing privacy.

1.4 This document

The main objective of this document, Project Management Plan (PMP) and Data Management Plan (DMP), is to collect, analyse and share the initial set up of simple rules for internal communication, in order to store them properly (where, how, who, title, version, revisions, use and storage etc.).

The data gathering and management is a continuous action throughout the duration of the project. This document evolved in order to follow the status of the project.

This document includes:

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_issue

² <https://www.myaccountingcourse.com/accounting-dictionary/ethical-issues>

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf

- Data Management Plan (DMP) (par 4)
 - Description on what kind and how data are collected, processed, maintained and shared during and after the end of the project;
 - A specific chapter dedicated to open access to research data.
- Project Management Plan (PMP) (par 6)
 - Internal communications: template for monthly electronic update (ANNEX 1).
 - Schedule management (ANNEX 2).
 - Financial and Resource management (ANNEX 3)
- A specific chapter dedicated to Data Security (par 4.10)
- A specific chapter dedicated to Social, Ethical, Legal, Privacy (par 5)

2. Project abstract

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers.

The basic idea underlying the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and qualitatively appropriate both to train the adequate number of workers and to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position: the technological RES potential can be reached by increasing hard and soft skills of potential users and stakeholders, developing interest in the topic and having clear and appropriate approaches, such as tools and learning modules using suitable language. Beside the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, it is important, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against lack of information, bad quality material, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills.

SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels:

1. Stakeholder community engagement
2. Knowledge sharing and peer learning
3. Skilling, upskilling, reskilling

SKILLBILL:

- i. analyses and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language;
- ii. creates several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice;
- iii. develops and implement innovative learning methods;
- iv. evaluates the work performed.

3. Project partners

Project partners are reported in the table below, along with the acronym.

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Acronymous	Country
1 (Coordinator)	AzeroCO2	A0	A0	IT
2	Q-PLAN International Advisors PC	Q-PLAN	QP	EL
3	White Research SRL	WR	WR	BE
4	Università della Tuscia	UniTus	UT	IT
5	Universidad de Sevilla	USE	US	ES
6	Metropolia ammattikorkeakoulu Oy	METROPOLIA	MT	FIN
7	Universiteit Utrecht	UU	UU	NL
8	European Renewable Energies Federation	EREF	ER	BE
9	SINERGIE	SIN	SI	IT
10	Pedal Consulting	PC	PC	SK

Table 1: project partners with acronymous

4. SKILLBILL Data Management Plan

As described in the project proposal, at the earliest opportunity and appropriate times, relevant data and information are to be made publicly available by presentation on the website, at the internal and external conferences and by publication in peer-reviewed journals, technical press and trade journals as well as the media campaign. Open data repository (i.e. Zenodo¹ for public deliverables) is used in order to documents being always available and open to increase knowledge transfer, connections and interest in RES, transparency and accessibility.

Open Science (OS) is both a policy priority of the European Commission and a required method of working under the EU research and innovation programs. OS contributes to the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of research.

SKILLBILL promotes OS in a threefold way:

- (1) as object of research and development,
- (2) as a principle, driver and strategy for its own inclusive and open practices, and
- (3) as a compliance rule under the Horizon Europe's Open Science.

4.1 Data Summary

This section is about the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project

4.1.1 *Types, formats and origin of data*

Data generated or collected during the project can be divided into the following groups:

- Data collected from stakeholders and interdisciplinary working groups during the mapping exercise.
- Data generated by project partners during the analysis and monitoring activities (such as feedback forms)
- Training materials and modules for MASTER and Vocational Education and Training (VET) purpose
- Data collected from MASTER and VET students
- Data collected from website use (subscribers, performance such analytics, website content)

¹ Zenodo builds a simple service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions, among others, to share and showcase research results. It is free of charge and accepts any file format.

- Data collected / generated from dissemination, communication (social media statistics, Data collected from project events (lists of participants for example)

All datasets created by the project are enlisted in a table; it is adjusted during project lifetime along with data requirements. An initial version of the table is given in ANNEX A: Dataset generated by the project;

The purpose of this data collection is to help achieve our main objectives of the project:

- To discuss on technological and non-technological barriers for RES penetration with the Quadruple Helix (industry, academia, government and civil society organisations) involvement (**WP2**)
- To push the development of the next-gen technology toward sustainability and circularity and to align priorities and needs in the whole chain (from designers, sellers, users, to dismantlers) (**WP2**);
- To develop an inclusive, dynamic and open depository and network for educational videos, interviews with business leaders and training lectures for each technology and several levels of details; (**WP3**)
- To launch an education program, European Master (**WP4**)
- To launch VET courses on line and/or using virtual reality (**WP5**)
- To promote knowledge sharing (**WP3, WP6**)
- To increase the value and involvement of female talent in technology, innovation and scientific research, combating stereotypes and gender discrimination, contributing to the orientation of young people to the jobs of the future and towards sustainable business models.

4.1.2 *Re-use any existing data and how*

While it is envisaged that most data collected are be open access and widely disseminated, some results of the project may need to be protected due to IP rights, that will be drafted in **D6.7 Exploitation and Sustainability Plan**, outlining the strategy for management of knowledge and **Intellectual Property (IP)** emerging from project activities, to maximise project's impact and systematically plan for their exploitation beyond project's lifetime.

When available, scientific and market-potential results are be promoted according to the **Exploitation strategy** (agreed at consortium level since the first project meeting), coherently with Open Access and IPR decisions, following EC & Horizon Europe guidelines and the Consortium Agreement.

In the last 6 months of project, all former activities are integrated by **specific measures to promote further project development beyond its end**.

The consortium will provide information on **what is needed in term of market exploitation**.

Measures used are mainly publications, repository on project website and open to transdisciplinary connections (e.g. participation in shared initiatives and platforms with other projects, EU and non-EU funded initiatives, project results capitalization and cross-fertilization activities for future projects).

Regarding the exploitation of results, the consortium is strongly focused on ensuring long-term exploitation of results, as we expect high market interest in the output, as the stakeholder connections (WP2), the Green Portal (WP3), the European Master (WP4), the VET modules (WP5). Hence the process to develop the exploitation plan includes a definition of specific needs and potential market of results and will produce a preliminary **Business Plan** that considers the exploitable results of the project such as the VR platform, the Master and VET courses and their development or maintenance (included in the Exploitation Plan WP6); the analysis is carried on in close relation with stakeholders and the Advisory Board. The collaboration with other project and research group fastens further development steps.

The Exploitation Plan will take advantage of the results of the dissemination activities and feedbacks from target audiences. The integration with Communication and Dissemination actions facilitates the **exploitation** of results and amplifies the effect of **communication**, raising **public awareness** on RES.

At project proposal level partners indicated a preliminary Exploitation Plans, that is developed in WP6, Task 6.3: Exploitation planning and IPR management; the deliverable D6.3 gives first a initial version of the Exploitation Plans at Month 6, then the final version at Month 36 will include the Business Plan.

4.1.3 Data utility

The data generated in the project are beneficial to a variety of stakeholders including policy makers, RES designers/ sellers/ users/ dismantlers, citizens, students and teachers/scientists. The data collected are relevant to key areas of project development and the information gathered help identify challenges in these areas and serve as an input for policy design at national and European level in these areas. Finally, the data inform the wider public about the developments and potential of the energy sector.

The table below summarizes data utility:

WP	Data collection	Target Stakeholder group	Data utility
WP2	During stakeholder working groups	RES designers, sellers, users, dismantlers; regulatory	Regulatory/ economic/ technological: at least 20 recommendations developed in the stakeholder joint initiative (5 per working group);
WP3	Discussion board in Green Portal,	technology developers, policy makers.	To understand the tech criticalities of a technology; To understand the non-tech issues of res penetration
WP3/WP6	Awareness material on RES Awareness material on gap gender	Students, Citizen, potential consumers, woman	To increase RES knowledge and involvement To decrease gap gender

WP4	from WP2: requests of the markets chain and skill gap analysis	Professors	To set up specific lesson's contents
WP5	from WP2: requests of the markets chain and skill gap analysis	Trainers	To set up the training programs flexible and empowering; To simplify the training process, speed up worker assimilation and cut back on employee management costs.
WP4/WP5	Data from training programs	Students, PA and technicians	To increase competences (skills, knowledge, abilities), and job expectations

Table 2: project initial data utility

4.2 FAIR data principles

FAIR Principles definition as referenced from FAIR principles description¹ are as follows:

To be Findable:

- F1. (meta)data² are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier of a Digital Object Identified (DOI) is issued to every published record on a trusted repository (e.g. Zenodo).
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource such as SKILLBILL website /Green Portal

To be Accessible:

- A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

¹ FAIR principles description: Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci. Data 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016).

²;"data that provides information about other data"; <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/metadata>

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:

- R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

4.3 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Almost all the data elaborated and released in SKILLBILL are documents such as the reports on the work performed, the material for EU Master (WP4) and VET (WP5). Other data are those included in the material uploaded on the Green Portal (WP3) and a video elaborated for communication purposes (WP6). To make those documents and data findable some descriptive metadata are used, such as: title, file name, abstract, author, and keywords.

4.3.1 Metadata

The metadata format follows the convention of the hosting research data repository. A draft metadata format is set out below and this is subject to review in the next DMP update.

If the data are included in documents, in the firsts page of the document, the following metadata are described:

General Information

- Title of the dataset/output/document
- Document ID
- Work Package
- Responsible Partner (using the naming convention in Table 1, par3)
- Author Information
- Document Type
- Dissemination Level
- Date of data collection/production/Issue Date
- The title of project and Funding sources that supported the collection of the data

Sharing/Access Information

- Dissemination Level
- Links to publications that cite or use the data

Dataset/Output Overview

- Version number
- Issue date
- Changes
- Keywords that describe the content

If the project data are included in a video, a hashtag (#) categorizes the following metadata:

- Relevant keyword
- Name of the Project
- The Label (elaborated in WP3; if applicable)

Relevant keyword

- The title of project and Funding source
- The type of RES
- The topic addressed

4.3.2 File naming

Descriptive file names are an important part of organizing, sharing, and keeping track of data files. The naming convention is based on elements that are important to the project. Files are named consistently:

File naming rules:

- Short but descriptive File names
- No special characters or spaces in a file name; the only special character to be used is the “.” in the version number
- Capitals and underscores instead of spaces or slashes
- Date format: YYYYMonthDD (month in letters, es: 2022May26) when required
- Version number at the end; further detail for correct numbering in the dedicated paragraph.
- Include name of the project
- Abbreviations: CA for “Consortium Agreement”, GA for “Grant Agreement”, D for “deliverable”, Min for “minutes”

EXAMPLE:

- CA_SKILLBILL_v01.00
- Min_SKILLBILL_2022Oct30_v01.00

For deliverables, use names as reported in table below:

Del. (n°)	Del. name in GA	Del. FILE name (for the first version)	Dissemination Level
D1.1	PMP and DMP	D1.1_SKILLBILL_PMP_DMP_v01.00	Public
D1.2	QA and RMP	D1.2_SKILLBILL_QA_RMP_v01.00	Public
D2.1	Stakeholder map and good practices	D2.1_SKILLBILL_StakeholderMap_v01.00	Public
D2.2	Co-design of joint stakeholder initiative	D2.2_SKILLBILL_CodesignStakeholderInitiative_v01.00	Public
D2.3	Actionable results from working groups and MML workshop	D2.3_SKILLBILL_WorkingGroups_MMLWorkshop_v01.00	Public
D3.1	Quality label definition	D3.1_SKILLBILL_QualityLabelDefinition_v01.00	Public
D4.1	Master syllabus	D4.1_SKILLBILL_MasterSyllabus_v01.00	Public
D4.2	Report on the first completed master cycle	D4.1_SKILLBILL_FirstMasterCycle_v01.00	Public
D5.1	Report on training needs analysis	D5.1_SKILLBILL_TrainingNeedsAnalysis_v01.00	Public
D5.2	Training programmes, storyboards and materials	D5.2_SKILLBILL_TrainingProgrammes_v01.00	Public
D5.3	Evaluation of training activities	D5.3_SKILLBILL_EvaluationTrainingActivities_v01.00	Public
D6.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	D6.1_SKILLBILL_DC_Plan_v01.00	Public
D6.2	Dissemination and Communication Results	D6.2_SKILLBILL_DC_Results_v01.00	Public
D6.3	Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability Plan	D6.3_SKILLBILL_ExploitationPlan_v01.00	Public
D6.4	Social impact monitoring methodology and assessment	D6.4_SKILLBILL_SocialImpact_v01.00	Public

Table 3: SKILLBILL list of deliverables

4.3.3 *Version File numbering*

To keep track of each time the document is revised, a file version is applied; the version control manages multiple variations of the same document, particularly when it is important to have record of how the document was created, developed and changed over time.

Each time the document is revised an identifier is applied, to identify the latest version of the document and differentiate between drafts and final approved versions. It is important to make sure all partners are always working in the correct version of a document.

- **'Revision' numbering system**

Any major changes to a file can be indicated by whole numbers, for example, v01 would be the first version, v02 the second version. Major revisions would be where the document has had significant changes or review and requires re-approval. Minor changes, such as typo, are indicated by increasing the decimal figure for example, v01.01 indicates a minor change has been made to the first version, and v03.01 a minor change has been made to the third version.

- **Leading 0s**

In order to facilitate sorting in numerical order; two decimals are used; es: 01.00; 02.00, ... 10, ... 100, etc." instead of "1, 2, ...10, 100, etc."

- **Sub-version**

When draft documents are sent out for revision, they should return carrying additional information to identify the project partner (using its short name in the table in par3) who has made the changes (sub-version). Example: a file with the name "min_2022May16__v01.00_XY" indicates that a colleague working for XY has made changes to the first version on May 16, 2022. The lead author would then add those changes to version v01 and rename the file following the revision numbering system. Changes to a draft document do not create a new version of the document, but a sub-version: several comments of a draft by several partners are identified by the file name; all the comments are gathered and eventually implemented in the draft: this creates a new version of the document.

- **'Version control table' with each important document**

The table keeps note of changes and their dates alongside the appropriate version number of the document.

- Final versions are saved as PDFs so that they are "fixed" and are not changeable. **The final version to be uploaded in the European portal.**
- Header/footer information are matched with the same version number as the file name.

The following example should clarify the rules above:

- “Example_draft_v01.00” is circulated by the document owner;
- partner A and partner B has few comments and create sub-versions:

“Example_draft_v01.00_2022Aug16_A” and “Example_draft_v01.00_2010Aug16_B”;

- the owner of the draft implements comments and create “Example_draft_v02.00”;
- this is circulated, accepted, generating “Example_v01.00”, stored as pdf and word document;
- Partner A want to introduce a new change:

this creates “Example_v01.01” for minor changes, or

“Example_v02.00” for major changes. In this case a second round of acceptance between partners is required.

Some documents that are working documents or they have been created to be updated regularly by the same author (e.g., monthly update excel, Paragraph 9), the change of versions is not required.

4.4 Making data accessible

Data collected and elaborated by project partners are stored in a trusted and shared repository. All public deliverables, training materials, journal articles and conference contributions are available on the project website or in the public repository. The public deliverables were identified in the project description.

Relevant datasets (without sensible data) are stored in ZENODO¹, which is the open access repository of the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe, OpenAIRE².

Data access policy are unrestricted since no confidentiality or Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues are expected regarding datasets used and elaborated in SKILLBILL; in any case, project partners confirmation is requested. All collected datasets is disseminated without an embargo period unless linked to a green open access publication.

Data objects are deposited in ZENODO under:

- Open access to data files and metadata and data files provided over standard protocols such as HTTP and Open Archive Initiative-Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).
- Use and reuse of data permitted.
- Privacy of its users protected.

¹<https://zenodo.org>

² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

4.5 Internal data collection

4.5.1 File storage

All the files produced are stored in a common space accessible to all partners. At first DROPBOX has been elected as the storage place.

The Dropbox space has been divided into folders, one for each WP; each WP leader is responsible for the organization of the files in the specific folder. In the folder, working documents and the final document should be easily accessible.

Previous versions of the documents are stored in a folder named “old” in the original folder; subversions of the documents are not stored for space limit reasons; all versions should be maintained for reference.

Figures below for examples:

Figure 1: screenshot of Dropbox repository for SKILLBILL

4.6 Making data interoperable

The official reports and the deliverables describe the data collected and elaborated during the SKILLBILL project.

All documents are identifiable based on a common naming convention, described in the dedicated paragraph (par. 4.3.2). Version control is clearly identified and follows the version control set out in dedicated paragraph (par. 4.3.3).

To ensure document and data control, each document and data set shall be uniquely identifiable. Each deliverable and data set must be associated to unique document name to ensure version control. The deliverable and data identifier must be used in the deliverable filename.

Data are collected and shared in a standardised way using a standard format for that data type. As required, references are made to any software required to run it. Given the scope of this project, it is anticipated that publicly available software are used to store data. Barriers to access through interoperability issues are not anticipated.

4.7 Increase data re-use

Part of the WP3's activities deal with the validation and re-organization of existing data, information and scientific communication materials with the aim to spread knowledge.

The methodology was drawn during the WP and described in the final version of D3.1 "Quality label definition".

4.8 Other research outputs

During project implementation, in WP4 and WP5 virtual reality and augmented reality software have been implemented.

For VIRTUAL REALITY PRACTICES AND TESTS: the minimum viable software (not a market-ready product) is released with suitable licensing model, favouring open source. This solution uses 3D-modeled virtual environments, containing interactive objects and simulations related to the subject. The training software is used through VR headsets and other electronic devices.

Metropolia aims to exploit its existing open SmarLab ecosystem environment and build on that when possible.

After the end of the project, the outputs from WP4 and WP5 will self-provide (e.g. through sponsorships and students fees) the resources for continuous improvement of new teaching activities and VR software/hardware update.

The process to develop the exploitation plan include a definition of specific needs and potential market of results and will produce a **Business Plan** for VR/AR platform Master and VET development maintenance (included in the Exploitation Plan WP6)

The SKILLBILL outputs and assets is identified through the D6.7 Exploitation and Sustainability Plan outlining the strategy for management of knowledge and Intellectual Property (IP) emerging from project activities, to maximise project's impact and systematically plan for their exploitation beyond project's lifetime.

4.9 Allocation of resources

The activities related to making the data/outputs open access is covered within the allocated budget for each work package.

Financial resources (Table 3.1h of project proposal) have been allocated to almost all project partners to cover expenses for open access papers publication; under “Other goods, works and services”, WP6.

- 1-AzzeroCO2 (A0): WP6: open access for papers publications: 1x2.800 €
- 2-Q-PLAN (QP): WP6: open access for papers publications: 1x2.800€
- 4- UNITUSCIA (UNITUS): WP6: open access for papers publications: 1x2.800 €
- 5- UNI SEVILLA (USE): WP6: open access for papers publications: 1x2.800€
- 6- METROPOLIA (MET): WP6: open access for papers publications: 1x2.800 €
- 7- UNI UTRECH (UU): WP6: open access for papers publications: 1x2.800€
- 9- SINERGIE (SIN): WP6: open access for papers publications: 1x2.800 €
- 10- PEDAL CONSULTING (PC): WP6: open access for papers publications: 1x2.800 €

AzzeroCO2 is responsible for the data management in SKILLBILL.

White Research, coordinator of WP6 assumes the roles of the **Communication and Exploitation Manager** of the project, it is in charge of developing, executing, and overseeing communication systems, whether internal or external, that effectively describe and promote the project:

- Identify Stakeholders.
- Plan Communications and Exploitation activities.
- Distribute Information.
- Manage Stakeholder Expectations.
- Report Performance.

4.10 Data security

During the development of the project, in all cases, no sensitive data (e.g., person’s racial origin; political opinions or religious or other beliefs; physical or mental health; sexual life; criminal convictions or the alleged commission of an offence; trade union membership) were required.

Some activities in the context of the project imply personal data collection, such as:

- Meetings and events organization
- Website/ Green Portal eventual registration and access (if a registration module is present)
- Master enrolment
- VET enrolment
- Stakeholder enrolment
- Feedback forms

The selection of feedback participants is implemented through standard sampling rules. Participants in the feedback are informed about the use that the project will make of data. These data are used

for social and statistical analysis and only aggregate data are considered public. If the feedbacks collect information such as income, gender, age, geographical location, the information is anonymized (i.e. people identified only by a code, not by their name/surname etc.).

To keep track of the participation in the events/courses and to have the evidence of the actual involvement, attendance sheets are used; participants to the events/courses are asked for name and signature for project deliverables purposes only and not be used for commercial purposes. In any case, no sensible or personal data (such as name, surname, e-mails of the participants in the training) appear in the Deliverables.

Participants are also informed that pictures taken during the events could be used for communication purpose and for website and reports. Participants are asked if they want to receive newsletters or communications.

Data collected and used in the project are safely stored and not externally shared, unless expressly required and after data owner consensus. In all phases/parts of the project where needed, data collection takes place informing individuals concerning:

- methods used for handling, storing and protecting personal data;
- research related justification for requesting/obtaining their data;
- guarantees concerning the rightful use of data;
- guarantees that participation is voluntary.

Dropbox, as project internal depository, maintains previous versions and deleted files for a short period of time.

All data, information and support material generated within the project are centrally stored on AzeroCO2 servers using their standard archiving data control procedures and routinely backed up (at least every six months) onto secure areas on a central server, according to standard policies and procedures. The folder in the server is regulated by a password, if required by project partners. A specific person nominated within the administration team holds management responsibility for these activities.

Loss of data is safeguarded against by:

- storing the data on secure servers supervised by project partners' host institutions;
- regular backing up of the data on the abovementioned servers;

Each involved partner takes all the actions needed to make sure that data use is strictly limited to the purposes specified in the project, and that such usage is limited to lawful activities. Intra-EU data transfers (only across partners involved in the project) is possible, and only if deemed as strictly needed for the purposes of the project.

5. Social, Ethical, Legal, Privacy issue

As described in the “Ethics self-assessment” of the project proposal, the beneficiaries ensure that the activities performed during the project life DO NOT:

- (a) aim at human cloning for reproductive purposes;
- (b) intend to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such changes heritable (with the exception of research relating to cancer treatment of the gonads, which may be financed),
- (c) intend to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer.

In addition to that, the beneficiaries ensure they will respect the fundamental principle of research integrity - as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. This implies compliance with the following fundamental principles:

- reliability in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources;
- honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way;
- respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment;
- accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts.

Beneficiaries ensure that persons carrying out activities in the project follow the good research practices and refrain from the research integrity violations described in this Code.

During project activities some surveys, feedbacks and interviews are envisaged; those do not include any sensitive data.

- **VET training courses and the European Master register personal information. Those data are handled with appropriate confidentiality and technical security, as required by national regulations and the EU legal framework.**

In case that interviews, focus groups, surveys, feedbacks conducted, eventual AB meeting recordings, procedures for selection of students and recruitment of participants to VET require personal data, the informed consent should be applied prior to the commencement of any relevant task.

If personal data are to be collected, then detailed information are provided on the procedures implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation, as well as whether personal data are involved.

A generic framework of protection measures is described in the Consortium Agreement, containing Information to be provided on the procedures that are implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation.

As specified by rules of good scientific practice the data are only collected and processed after receiving informed consent from the data providers, such as interviewees during stakeholder consultations. Informed consent is requested for using, sharing, and long-term storing the provided information. It includes consent about the nature, method, goal and possible risks or stress of the research, and voluntary character of participation.

Work Package leaders ensure that only data that are necessary to achieve the defined goals are collected by respective partners.

Personal data are collected in the form of names of the interviewees or participants and of the organisations they represent. This data are made anonymous in the processing stage of research to limit the interviewees' identification. The original personal data are stored separately on servers provided by the host institution of the partner which collected the data under access restricted to project partners. Upon consent of each interviewee, personal data can be used in data publicly distributed by the project.

The informed consent procedure includes:

- an information sheet with a description of the project and its objectives, a detailed information on the purposes of the analysis, advice on unrestricted disclaimer rights on their agreement so that the potential participants can make an informed, voluntary and rational decision to participate; the informed consent of the participants is provided to them prior to their agreement for the collection of information from them,
- an informed consent form to be signed by the participants, including a description of their rights according to the respective data protection law; the information that collected collected, how this information is used, processed and stored and retention periods, alongside activities (such as dissemination activities) that make use of this information, basic principles on which the collection, storage, and processing is based on.

5.1 Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislations

As described in the "Ethics self-assessment" of the project proposal, SKILLBILL guarantees that all partners follow EU and national regulations regarding data protection. The consortium partners are aware of EU's legislation regarding ethics, privacy, and security, and are committed to adhering to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR (EU) 2016/679).

All activities are carried out ensuring the ethical principles in accordance with Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament, about the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, as well as Directive 2002/58/EC, concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector, as modified by Directive 2009/136/EC. All national and data protection and privacy laws for different EU countries are also followed.

All activities of the project follow:

- Legal requirements derived principally from the GDPR;
- The Model Grant Agreement rules on ethical issues in Articles 13 (Confidentiality and Security), 14 (Ethics and Values), and 15 (Data Protection) are considered as the basic regulation;
- The results of the Ethics Review and subsequent Ethics Requirements; in case, the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement reflect them, and the project management will be compliant;
- The project collects and processes required data only if it is necessary.

5.2 Gender equality

The consortium addresses sex, gender, and equality issues early on in the proposal phase. The consortium respectful of gender equality and ensure there is no discrimination on the basis of a person's gender during the project's activities.

In case, gender biases in the field are identified and eliminated.

SKILLBILL addresses specifically the gender gaps and aims to eliminate them with several activities, tools and appropriate language.

6. SKILLBILL Project Management Plan

The SKILLBILL governance structure is described in the Consortium Agreement, signed by all the partners. Below extracts of the chapter 6 are reported:

6.1 Project Management general structure, roles and responsibilities

The organisational structure of the consortium shall comprise the following Consortium Bodies:

- The TECHNICAL COORDINATION COMMITTEE (TCC),
- The ADVISORY BOARD (AB).

The management key roles are:

- The PROJECT MANAGER (PM),
- The COMMUNICATION MANAGER (CM),
- The WORK PACKAGE LEADERS (WPL).

- The **TECHNICAL COORDINATION COMMITTEE (TCC)** is the decision-making body of the consortium; hereinafter “**TCC**” The **TCC** has direct technical control of all activities within the PROJECT; it shall be composed by a representative from each PARTY of the Consortium and is chaired by the Coordinator.
- The **ADVISORY BOARD (AB)**, composed by stakeholders, assists the TCC and the CM providing suggestions on inputs and outputs and supporting the communication and dissemination activities.
- The **PROJECT MANAGER (PM)** is a staff member of the Coordinator; he/she is responsible for the administrative and consortium management activities, in order to organize, plan, monitor and control project progress and to manage resources.
- The **COMMUNICATION MANAGER (CM)**, represents the leader of **WP6** and assume the roles of the Communication and exploitation Manager of the project.
- The **WORK PACKAGE LEADER (WPL)** is nominated by the PARTY appointed for managing the Work Package and is responsible for coordinating the work with all the Parties involved.

6.1.1 *The Coordinator*

The **Coordinator** is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the Coordinator shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement;
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available;

- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certification) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority;
- preparing the meetings, proposing decisions and preparing the agenda of TCC meetings, chairing the meetings, preparing the minutes of the meetings and monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings;
- transmitting promptly documents and information connected with the Project to any other Party concerned;
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks;
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims;
- nominating the **PROJECT MANAGER (PM)** as the reference person for all the Parties and the Granting Authority.

If the Coordinator fails in its coordination tasks, the TCC may propose to the Granting Authority to change the Coordinator.

The Coordinator shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other Party or of the consortium, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the Grant Agreement or this Consortium Agreement.

The Coordinator shall not enlarge its role beyond the tasks specified in this Consortium Agreement and in the Grant Agreement.

6.1.2 *The TCC*

The TCC shall consist of one representative of each Party (hereinafter referred to as “Member”).

Each Member shall be deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in this section of the Consortium Agreement. Decisions are made by TCC.

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the TCC, unless decided otherwise by the TCC.

The Parties agree to abide by all decisions of the TCC.

This does not prevent the Parties from exercising their veto rights, according to the relative section of the CA, or from submitting a dispute for resolution in accordance with the provisions of settlement of disputes in the Consortium Agreement.

Any Member of the TCC:

- should be present or represented at any meeting;
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting;
- and shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

The TCC, shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out herein.

The following decisions shall be taken by the TCC:

a) Content, finances and intellectual property rights

b) Evolution of the consortium

- Entry of a new Party to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party
- Withdrawal of a Party from the Project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal
- Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement
- Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
- Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party
- Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the consortium and measures relating thereto
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the Coordinator
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement

c) Appointments

- Appointment of Advisory Board Members.

In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the TCC, Members shall rearrange the tasks of the Parties concerned. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration any prior legitimate commitments which cannot be cancelled.

6.1.3 *Advisory Board (AB)*

An Advisory Board (AB) is appointed and steered by the TCC. The AB shall assist and facilitate the decisions made by the TCC.

The Coordinator ensures that a non-disclosure agreement is executed between all Parties and each AB member.

The Coordinator shall write the minutes of the AB meetings and submit them to the TCC. The AB members shall be allowed to participate in TCC meetings upon invitation but have not any voting rights.

6.2 Project schedule

The overall project schedule management is the responsibility of the Project Coordinator; the schedule management within each WP is managed by the WP leader in collaboration with the specific task leaders.

In order to allow the PC to closely follow the project implementation the beneficiary fills every month the template for monthly electronic update and consult the Work Breakdown Structure for incoming deadlines (see 6.5.2).

If the PC identifies schedule changes and critical points, they work with the WP leader and the TCC in order to identify the best way to get the project back on schedule.

For important delays, i.e. more than 2 months, the TCC and PC inform the Project Officer in order to decide how to proceed.

6.3 Project budget

As specified in the Consortium Agreement, the financial contribution is distributed by the Project Coordinator according to

- the assigned budget;
- the approval of reports or potential amendments.

More details can be found in the Consortium Agreement and in the Grant Agreement

The cost management ensures that the project is completed within budget. Cost Management refers to the process of gathering, tracking and managing the financial resources throughout the project's life cycle. This process relies on accurate estimates and actual data that need to be updated accordingly. In order to have a clear understanding of the budget implementation the tool Financial and Resource management (see 6.5.3) is in place. Having quality input data is the key to obtaining reliable cost information for managing resources and making decisions. Cost summaries information at the different levels are rolled up from task level to the project level.

In order to keep track of the estimated and real budget spent, each beneficiary, provides financial data continuously (at least every 6 months), where real personnel costs, other direct costs and indirect costs during the period are indicated. Each beneficiary is responsible to control their costs in accordance with their own accounting and management principles and practices.

The PC shall prepare a status update every 6 months (to be presented during the project meetings), in order to avoid any problem and have mitigation actions ready.

6.4 Internal communication

6.4.1 *Contact list*

An excel file named "SKILLBILL_Contacts" stored in the project general folder in Dropbox contains the updated contact list of the beneficiaries. Project beneficiaries should keep the file regularly updated. Access rights and roles within the project are set based on the information provided in the contact file. A general mailing list containing the beneficiaries contacts has been defined.

6.4.2 *Meetings*

The consortium meetings are planned every six months providing the discussion platform where all beneficiaries can meet and discuss ongoing work, outputs and next steps to be taken. Each meeting is organized by one beneficiary that is responsible for venue, agenda (in collaboration with the coordinator), potential co-located events and invitation of external guests. Focus of these meetings is mainly on the following aspects:

- Plenary sessions to summarize the project's outputs and lessons learned; definition of actions and measures to meet the project's objectives; progress reporting and review preparations.
- WP related sessions to define WP related actions, issues and contingency measures.

The beneficiaries could also meet in different subgroups to plan and discuss specific parts of work and collaboration efforts with respect to their WPs and tasks.

6.5 Project management tools

6.5.1 *Template for monthly electronic update*

The monthly electronic update is a simple file created in order to easily monitor the status of the project, to avoid unforeseen risks or delays and to circulate information between partners.

The template in Annex 1 is distributed between partners. Each partner is expected to fill its own table with all the info available on the ongoing work or to be set up each month. For this file no file version is required.

The Project Manager asks by email at the beginning of every month to send the table with the info at the end of the same months.

The table is collected and stored in the shared folder for future references as described in the dedicated paragraph.

6.5.2 *Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)*

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS): Project's commitments: an Excel file evidencing all project's milestone, outputs, deliverables and results, timelines, in order to monitor the effective project progress.

This file is prepared by the Coordinator and each project partner is supposed to update it on a regular basis (at least every 6 months by each partner); each partner has its own file in a separate Dropbox folder with restricted access. To update this file no versions are required.

The template is given in Annex 2

The file has been divided into several macro actions, based on SKILLBILL activities, such as:

- Deliverable preparation,
- Deliverable update,
- Milestone,
- Project meeting,
- Tasks,
- Group formation,
- EU report,
- Feedback,
- Workshop,
- Web

Each macro activities are composed by some micro activities; the final micro activity is the end of the macro activity (date). The already defined dates that cannot be changed are in grey. The other dates are calculated in cascade, in function of the activity to be performed; this forms a set of chronological order of activities to be performed and a date to start the activity. This is just for reference and not compulsory, in order to monitor project progress and reduce risks of delays.

Each partner has a dedicated sheet; Each partner can use it to monitor the progress of their activities. In particular:

- the YELLOW, ORANGE and RED statuses (which correspond to activities respectively "in progress", "close to due" and "expired") are updated automatically, based on the planning made.
- the GREEN status (which corresponds to "completed" activities, even late ones) is "effective". An activity becomes "completed" only after verification made by AzzeroCO2.

In addition to the sheet for the partners, one sheet is dedicated to the Gantt, one to Deliverables and one to Milestones, with actual real dates of accomplishment. One sheet (ALL) is a recap of all the partners activities; the data are linked to the original pages, so it is automatically updated; this is created in order to have the project overview and to have the possibility to filter data.

One final sheet has been dedicated to the project objectives, indicators and results.

6.5.3 *Financial and Resource management*

An Excel file evidencing all project's budget, expenditures and progress.

This file is prepared by the Coordinator and each project partner is supposed to update it on a regular basis.

The template is given in Annex 3.

Each partner has a dedicated sheet; each partner can use it to monitor the progress of their expenditures. In particular:

- Personnel, inserting additional required information to calculate efforts and the time sheets
- The other type of costs.

The file checks if the amount is referred to the appropriate WP giving warning alerts both for the type of cost, the WP number and the amount.

The file calculates the advancement (%).

One sheet (ALL) is a recap of all the partners activities; the data are linked to the original pages, so it is automatically updated; this is created in order to have the project overview and to have the possibility to filter data.

If the template is not compatible with administrative practices/rules of some specific partners, some adjustment may be implemented in their file to collect all the required information.

7. Conclusion & deviations

The original Project Management Plan and Data Management Plan proved to be suitable for the purpose and was followed throughout the project.

The only minor deviation from the DMP was:

- In the second part of the project some Partners had space issues in the Dropbox repository. For that reason, some documents were moved to the project Drive folder.

The main criticality in the PMP procedures was:

- In some cases, Partners delayed the production of their MEUs by few (max 3) months. The information has been verified and it didn't affect the project; in addition, AzeroCO2 was involved in all the WPs and thus always aware of the progress of the activities. Nevertheless, the management procedure and all the periodic tools were considered useful and effective and thus the plan wasn't modified.

8. ANNEX A: Dataset generated by the project

The annex is a working document FILE EXCEL. When updated, no need to change the name of the file, unless substantial changes to the file structure are done; the attachment provided is the pdf version

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
1	WP	DOCUMENT NAME	BRIEF DOCUMENT DESCRIPTION	DOCUMENT FORMAT	DATA SIZE	DATA UTILITY <small>(see chapter 4 of D1.1)</small>	METADATA <small>(see chapter 5,2 of D1.1)</small>	PRIVACY REQUIREMENTS <small>(see chapter 8 of D1.1)</small>	DISSEMINATION LEVEL	DEPOSITORY				
2														
3														
4														
5														
6														
7														
8														
9														
10														
11														
12														
13														
14														
15														

Figure 2: screenshot of the file “Dataset”

9. ANNEX 1: Monthly update

The annex is a working document FILE EXCEL. Each partner has its own file to update; when updated, no need to change the name of the file, unless substantial changes to the file structure are done; the attachment provided is the pdf version

VP N°	VP name	sub-task N°	sub-task name	Leading Partner	Activity(ies) performed	activity(s) description	Status (started, ongoing, concluded)	Outputs
VP1	Coordination And Management	11	Strategic, technical, financial coordination	A0				
VP1	Coordination And Management	12	Quality assurance and risk management	A0				
VP1	Coordination And Management	13	Ethics and data management	A0				
VP1	Coordination And Management	14	Advisors Board organization	A0				
VP1	Coordination And Management	15	Verification of appreciation and awareness	A0				
VP2	STAKEHOLDERE JOINT INITIATIVE	2.1	Stakeholder community mapping and user research to better appreciate current training needs and skilling practices	VR				
VP2	STAKEHOLDERE JOINT INITIATIVE	2.2	Co-design of stakeholder joint initiative	GP				
VP2	STAKEHOLDERE JOINT INITIATIVE	2.3	Set up, operation and coordination of working groups	GP				
VP2	STAKEHOLDERE JOINT INITIATIVE	2.4	Mobilization and mutual learning based on working group outcomes	PC				
VP3	GREEN KNOWLEDGE SHARING	3.1	Quality label	A0				
VP3	GREEN KNOWLEDGE SHARING	3.2	Green portal organization	A0				
VP3	GREEN KNOWLEDGE SHARING	3.3	Green portal launch, population and sustain	A0				
VP4	INTERNATIONAL MASTER	4.1	Administrative organization	UniTus				
VP4	INTERNATIONAL MASTER	4.2	Infrastructure equipment	UniTus				
VP4	INTERNATIONAL MASTER	4.3	Content design	UniTus				
VP4	INTERNATIONAL MASTER	4.4	Didactic organization	UniTus				
VP4	INTERNATIONAL MASTER	4.5	Master delivery to students	UniTus				
VP4	INTERNATIONAL MASTER	4.6	Master promotional activity	UniTus				
VP5	VET	5.1	Segmentation and training needs analysis	SIN				
VP5	VET	5.2	Curriculum and content design	SIN				

Figure 3: screenshot of the file “Monthly update “

10. ANNEX 2: Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)

The annex is a working document FILE EXCEL. When updated, no need to change the name of the file, unless substantial changes to the file structure are done; the attachment provided is the pdf version

Figure 4: screenshot of the file “Work Breakdown Structure“

ANNEX 2: Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)									
WP	Type of activity	Specification	Task leader	Activity owner	Activities	Start date	End date	Current status	Notes
WP1	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D1.1 a PMP and DMP (initial release)	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Preparation draft			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31 October 2022	To start	
WP1	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D1.2 a QA & RM (initial release)	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Preparation draft			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		30 November 2022	To start	
WP1	DELIVERABLE UPDATE	D1.1 b PMP and DMP (second release)	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	UPDATE DELIVERABLE			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31 August 2025	To start	
WP1	DELIVERABLE UPDATE	D1.2 b QA & RM (second release)	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	UPDATE DELIVERABLE			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31 August 2025	To start	

WP1	MILESTONE	M1 Data Management Plan available	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check Means of verification MILESTONE			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Share comments with partner, if any			To start
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Submission MILESTONE		30 November 2022	To start
WP1	MILESTONE	M3 Advisory Board formed	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check Means of verification MILESTONE			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Share comments with partner, if any			To start
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Submission MILESTONE		28 February 2023	To start
WP1	GROUP FORMATION	AB Advisory Board formed	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Request name to partners			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Decide names with partner			To start
				All partners	Send requests to AB members			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Implement AB			To start
				AzzeroCO2	AB formed		28 February 2023	To start
WP1	Feedback	D4.2 Report on the first completed master cycle	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Feedback forms elaborated (M6)		01 February 2023	To start
				AzzeroCO2	Initial evaluation for baseline (M8)		01 April 2023	To start
				All partners	Middle check (M20)		01 April 2024	To start
				AzzeroCO2	Final check (M30-34)		01 February 2025	To start
				AzzeroCO2	Analise and finalise chapter report		31 August 2025	To start
WP1	Feedback	D5.3	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Feedback forms elaborated (M6)		01 February 2023	To start

		Evaluation of training activities		AzzeroCO2	Initial evaluation for baseline (M8)		01 April 2023	To start	
				All partners	Middle check (M20)		01 April 2024	To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Final check (M30-34)		01 February 2025	To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Analise and finalise chapter report		31 May 2025	To start	
WP1	Feedback	D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Results	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Feedback forms elaborated (M6)		01 February 2023	To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Initial evaluation for baseline (M8)		01 April 2023	To start	
				All partners	Middle check (M20)		01 April 2024	To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Final check (M30-34)		01 February 2025	To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Analise and finalise chapter report		31 August 2025	To start	
MIX	1 EU REPORT	EU REPORT	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Preparation draft			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission REPORT		30 April 2024	To start	
MIX	2 EU REPORT	EU REPORT	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Preparation draft			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission REPORT		31 October 2025	To start	
MIX	PROJECT MEETING	1-KICK OFF	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check room/consortium availability			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	fix data			To start	
				All partners	book travel, hotel, room			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	prepare meeting			To start	

				AzzeroCO2	MEETING		14 September 2022	To start	
MIX	PROJECT MEETING	2-meeting	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check room/consortium availability			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	fix data			To start	
				All partners	book travel, hotel, room			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	prepare meeting			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	MEETING		01 February 2023	To start	
MIX	PROJECT MEETING	3-meeting	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check room/consortium availability			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	fix data			To start	
				All partners	book travel, hotel, room			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	prepare meeting			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	MEETING		01 August 2023	To start	
MIX	PROJECT MEETING	4-meeting	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check room/consortium availability			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	fix data			To start	
				All partners	book travel, hotel, room			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	prepare meeting			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	MEETING		01 February 2024	To start	
MIX	PROJECT MEETING	5-meeting	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check room/consortium availability			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	fix data			To start	
				All partners	book travel, hotel, room			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	prepare meeting			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	MEETING		01 August 2024	To start	
MIX	PROJECT MEETING	6-meeting	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check room/consortium availability			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	fix data			To start	

				All partners	book travel, hotel, room			To start
				AzzeroCO2	prepare meeting			To start
				AzzeroCO2	MEETING		01 February 2025	To start
				AzzeroCO2	check room/consortium availability			To start
				AzzeroCO2	fix data			To start
MIX	PROJECT MEETING	7-meeting/ final	AzzeroCO2	All partners	book travel, hotel, room			To start
				AzzeroCO2	prepare meeting			To start
				AzzeroCO2	MEETING		01 June 2025	To start

WP2	Type of activity	Specification	Task leader	Activity owner	Activities	Start date	End date	Current status	Notes
WP2	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D2.1 Stakeholder map and good practices	WR	WR	Preparation draft			To start	
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				WR	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31 May 2023	To start	
WP2	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D2.2 Co-design of joint stakeholder initiative	QP	QP	Preparation draft			To start	
				QP	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				QP	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31 August 2023	To start	
WP2	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D2.3 a Actionable results from working groups and MML workshop (initial release)	QP	QP	Preparation draft			To start	
				QP	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				QP/PC	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31 August 2024	To start	
WP2	DELIVERABLE UPDATE	D2.3 b Actionable results from working groups and MML workshop (final release)	QP	QP	UPDATE DELIVERABLE			To start	
				QP	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				WR	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31 August 2025	To start	
WP2	MILESTONE	M6	QP	QP	check Means of verification MILESTONE			To start	

		First Stakeholder joint initiative		QP	Share comments with partner, if any			To start	
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			To start	
				QP	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission MILESTONE		30 June 2023	To start	
WP2	Workshop	first MML workshop	PC	PC	check Means of verification MILESTONE			To start	
				PC	Share comments with partner, if any			To start	
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			To start	
				PC	Implement comments			To start	
				PC	organized by M28		1 December 2024	To start	
WP2	Workshop	second MML workshop	PC	PC	check Means of verification MILESTONE			To start	
				PC	Share comments with partner, if any			To start	
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			To start	
				PC	Implement comments			To start	
				PC	the second workshop will be organized on M34.		1 June 2025	To start	
WP2	TASK	2.1 Stakeholder community mapping and user research to better appreciate current training needs and skilling practices (M1 – M9; Leader: WR, support by: all partners)	WR	WR	Set up the work with partners	1 September 2022		To start	
				WR	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				WR	Monitor inputs			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		31 August 2025	To start	
WP2	TASK	2.2 Co-design of stakeholder joint initiative	QP	QP	Set up the work with partners	1 March 2023		To start	
				QP	Receive inputs			To start	

		(M7 – M12; Leader: QP, support by: all partners)		All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				QP	Monitor inputs			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		28 February 2026	To start	
WP2	TASK	2.3 Set up, operation and coordination of working groups (M10–36; Leader: QP, support by: all)	QP	QP	Set up the work with partners	1 June 2023		To start	
				QP	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				QP	Monitor inputs			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		31 May 2026	To start	
WP2	TASK	2.4 Mobilization and mutual learning based on working group outcomes (M13-36; Leader: PC, support by: all partners)	PC	PC	Set up the work with partners	1 September 2023		To start	
				PC	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				PC	Monitor inputs			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		31 August 2026	To start	

WP	Type of activity	Specification	Task leader	Activity owner	Activities	Start date	End date	Notes
WP3	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D3.1 Quality label definition	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Preparation draft			
				AzzeroCO2	Share draft with partner			
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			
			AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		28 February 2023		
WP3	green portal	WEB	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Preparation draft			
				AzzeroCO2	Share draft with partner			
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			
			AzzeroCO2	Platform active		1 February 2023		
WP3	MILESTONE	M4 Green Portal on line	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	check Means of verification MILESTONE			
				AzzeroCO2	Share comments with partner, if any			
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			
				AzzeroCO2	Implement comments			
			AzzeroCO2	Submission MILESTONE		28 February 2023		
WP3	TASK	3.1 Quality Label (M3-M36)	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	Appoint ABS	1 December 2022		
				AzzeroCO2	discuss with ABS on green label		continuous	
				All partners	evaluate material		continuous	
				AzzeroCO2	upload material		continuous	
			AzzeroCO2	Use green label		31 August 2025		
WP3	TASK	3.2 Green portal organization	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	search web manager	1 December 2022		

		(M3-M9)		All partners	web manager appointed		30 January 2023	
				All partners	search social influencer	1 December 2022		
				AzzeroCO2	social influencer appointed		1 March 2023	
				AzzeroCO2	Start advertisement		30 April 2023	
WP3	TASK	3.3 Green portal launch, population and sustain (M6-36)	AzzeroCO2	AzzeroCO2	ask for material to be uploaded	1 August 2025		
				All partners	send material (external)			
				All partners	send material (internal)			
				AzzeroCO2	check material (external)			
				AzzeroCO2	upload material		31 August 2025	

WP	Type of activity	Specification	Task leader	Activity owner	Activities	Start date	End date	Current status	Notes
WP4	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D4.1 Master syllabus	UNITUS	UNITUS	Preparation draft			To start	
				UNITUS	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				UNITUS	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-mag-23	To start	
WP4	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D4.2 Report on the first completed master cycle	UNITUS	UNITUS	Preparation draft			To start	
				UNITUS	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				UNITUS	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-ago-25	To start	
WP4	MILESTONE	M5 Master launched	UNITUS	UNITUS	check Means of verification MILESTONE			To start	
				UNITUS	Share comments with partner, if any			To start	
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			To start	
				UNITUS	Implement comments			To start	
				UNITUS	Submission MILESTONE		31-mag-23	To start	
WP4	TASK	4.1 Administrative organization (M01-M03)	UNITUS	UNITUS	Discussion with other Unis to set up work	01-set-22		To start	
				UNITUS	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Monitor inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Write on inputs		30-nov-22	To start	
WP4	TASK	4.2: Infrastructure equipment (M01-M12)	UNITUS	UNITUS	Set up the work with partners	01-set-22		To start	
				UNITUS	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Monitor inputs			To start	

				UNITUS	Write on inputs		31-ago-23	To start	
WP4	TASK	4.3 Content design (M03-M24)	UNITUS	UNITUS	Set up the work with partners	01-set-22		To start	
				UNITUS	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Monitor inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Write on inputs		01-ago-24	To start	
WP4	TASK	4.4: Didactic organization (M03-M09)	UNITUS	UNITUS	Set up the work with partners	01-nov-22		To start	
				UNITUS	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Monitor inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Write on inputs		31-mag-23	To start	
WP4	TASK	4.5 Master delivery to students (M12-M36)	UNITUS	UNITUS	Set up the work with partners	01-ago-23		To start	
				UNITUS	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Monitor inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Write on inputs		30-giu-25	To start	
WP4	TASK	4.6 Master promotional activity (M06-M36)	UNITUS	UNITUS	Set up the work with partners	01-feb-23		To start	
				UNITUS	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Monitor inputs			To start	
				UNITUS	Write on inputs		30-giu-25	To start	

WP	Type of activity	Specification	Task leader	Activity owner	Activities	Start date	End date	Current status	Notes
WP5	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D5.1 Report on training needs analysis	SIN	SIN	Preparation draft			To start	
				SIN	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				SIN	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		28-feb-23	To start	
WP5	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D5.2 a Training programmes, storyboards and materials (initial release)	SIN	SIN	Preparation draft			To start	
				SIN	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				SIN	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-dic-23	To start	
WP5	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D5.3 Evaluation of training activities	SIN	SIN	Preparation draft			To start	
				SIN	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				SIN	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-mag-25	To start	
WP5	DELIVERABLE UPDATE	D5.2 b Training programmes, storyboards and materials (final release)	SIN	SIN	UPDATE DELIVERABLE			To start	
				SIN	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				SIN	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-mag-25	To start	
WP5	MILESTONE	M7 Programmes and training contents ready (first version)	SIN	SIN	check Means of verification MILESTONE			To start	
				SIN	Share comments with partner, if any			To start	
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			To start	
				SIN	Implement comments			To start	

				AzzeroCO2	Submission MILESTONE		31-dic-23	To start	
WP5	TASK	5.1 Segmentation and training needs analysis (M2-6)	SIN	SIN	Set up the work with partners	01-ott-22		To start	
				SIN	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				SIN	Monitor inputs			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		01-feb-23	To start	
WP5	TASK	5.2 Curriculum and content design (M7-33)	SIN	SIN	Set up the work with partners	01-mar-23		To start	
				SIN	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				SIN	Monitor inputs			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		30-mag-25	To start	
WP5	TASK	5.3 Piloting and validation of training courses (M17-33)	SIN	SIN	Set up the work with partners	01-gen-24		To start	
				SIN	Receive inputs			To start	
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start	
				SIN	Monitor inputs			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		30-mag-25	To start	

WP	Type of activity	Specification	Task leader	Activity owner	Activities	Start date	End date	Current status	Notes
WP6	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D6.1a Dissemination and Communication Plan (initial release)	WR	WR	Preparation draft			To start	
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				WR	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-dic-22	To start	
WP6	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Results	WR	WR	Preparation draft			To start	
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				WR	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-ago-25	To start	
WP6	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D6.3 a Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability Plan (initial release)	WR	WR	Preparation draft			To start	
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				WR	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		28-feb-23	To start	
WP6	DELIVERABLE PREPARATION	D6.4 a Social impact monitoring methodology and assessment (initial release)	WR	WR	Preparation draft			To start	
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments			To start	
				WR	Implement comments			To start	
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		29-feb-24	To start	
WP6	WEB		WR	WR	Preparation draft			To start	
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start	
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start	
				WR	Implement comments			To start	
				WR	Platform active		31-dec-22	To start	

WP6	DELIVERABLE UPDATE	D6.1 b Dissemination and Communication Plan (initial release)	WR	WR	UPDATE DELIVERABLE			To start
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start
				All partners	Send comments to DEL owner			To start
				WR	Implement comments			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		29-feb-24	To start
WP6	DELIVERABLE UPDATE	D6.3 b Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability Plan (final release)	WR	WR	UPDATE DELIVERABLE			To start
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start
				All partners	Send comments			To start
				WR	Implement comments			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-ago-25	To start
WP6	DELIVERABLE UPDATE	D6.4 b Social impact monitoring methodology and assessment (final release)	WR	WR	UPDATE DELIVERABLE			To start
				WR	Share draft with partner			To start
				All partners	Send comments			To start
				WR	Implement comments			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Submission DELIVERABLE		31-ago-25	To start
WP6	MILESTONE	M8 Final dissemination event	WR	WR	check Means of verification MILESTONE			To start
				WR	Share comments with partner, if any			To start
				All partners	Replay to comments, if any			To start
				WR	Implement comments			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Submission MILESTONE		31-ago-25	To start
WP6	TASK	6.1 Dissemination and communication strategy and plan (M1-M36) (Leader: WR, support by: All)	WR	WR	Set up the work with partners	01-set-22		To start
				WR	Receive inputs			To start
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start
				WR	Monitor inputs			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		31-ago-25	To start

WP6	TASK	6.2: Dissemination and communication activities deployment (M1-M36) (Leader: WR, support by: All)	WR	WR	Set up the work with partners	01-set-22		To start
				WR	Receive inputs			To start
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start
				WR	Monitor inputs			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		31-ago-25	To start
WP6	TASK	6.3 Exploitation planning and IPR management (M1-M36) (Leader: WR, support by: All)	WR	WR	Set up the work with partners	01-set-22		To start
				WR	Receive inputs			To start
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start
				WR	Monitor inputs			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		31-ago-25	To start
WP6	TASK	6.4 Social impact monitoring (M12-M36; Leader: QP, support by: All)	QP	QP	Set up the work with partners	01-ago-23		To start
				QP	Receive inputs			To start
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start
				QP	Monitor inputs			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		31-ago-25	To start
WP6	TASK	6.5 Task 6.5: Synergies with related initiatives (M4-M36; Leader: WR, support by: All)	WR	WR	Set up the work with partners	01-dic-22		To start
				WR	Receive inputs			To start
				All partners	Implement inputs			To start
				WR	Monitor inputs			To start
				AzzeroCO2	Write on inputs		31-ago-25	To start

D1.1: Project Management Plan (PMP) and Data Management Plan (DMP), Version 04.01; 05/08/2025

Del. (n°)	Del. name	WP n°	Lead partner	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery date (months)	Delivery date	START DATE
								01/09/2022
D1.1 a	PMP and DMP (initial version)	1	A0	DMP	PU	2	31/10/2022	
D1.1 b	PMP and DMP (final version)	1	A0	DMP	PU	36	31/08/2025	
D1.2 a	QA & RM (initial version)	1	A0	R	PU	3	30/11/2022	
D1.2 b	QA & RM (final version)	1	A0	R	PU	36	31/08/2025	
D2.1	Stakeholder map and good practices	2	WR	R	PU	9	31/05/2023	
D2.2	Co-design of joint stakeholder initiative	2	QP	R	PU	12	31/08/2023	
D2.3 a	Actionable results from working groups and MML workshop (initial ver.)	2	QP/PC	R	PU	24	31/08/2024	
D2.3 b	Actionable results from working groups and MML workshop (fin. ver.)	3	QP/PC	R	PU	36	31/08/2025	
D3.1	Quality label definition	3	A0	R	PU	6	28/02/2023	
D4.1	Master syllabus	4	Unitus	R	PU	9	31/05/2023	
D4.2	Report on the first completed master cycle	4	Unitus	R	PU	36	31/08/2025	
D5.1	Report on training needs analysis	5	SIN	R	PU	6	28/02/2023	
D5.2 a	Training programmes, storyboards and materials (initial ver.)	5	SIN	R	PU	16	31/12/2023	
D5.2 b	Training programmes, storyboards and materials (final ver.)	5	SIN	R	PU	33	31/05/2025	
D5.3	Evaluation of training activities	5	SIN	R	PU	33	31/05/2025	
D6.1a	Dissemination and Communication Plan (initial ver.)	6	WR	R	PU	4	31/12/2022	
D6.1 b	Dissemination and Communication Plan (final ver.)	6	WR	R	PU	18	29/02/2024	
D6.2	Dissemination and Communication Results	6	WR	R	PU	36	31/08/2025	
D6.3 a	Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability Plan (initial ver.)	6	WR	R	PU	6	28/02/2023	
D6.3 b	Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability Plan (final ver.)	7	WR	R	PU	36	31/08/2025	
D6.4 a	Social impact monitoring methodology and assessment (initial ver.)	6	QP	R	PU	18	29/02/2024	

D6.4 b	Social impact monitoring methodology and assessment (final ver.)	7	QP	R	PU	36	31/08/2025
	1 EU REPORT					20	30/04/2024
	2 EU REPORT					38	31/10/2025

Mil. N°	Milestone name	Related work package(s)	Due date (in month)	Means of verification	Delivery date	START DATE
						01/09/2022
M1	Data Management plan	WP1	3	Document available	30/11/2022	
M2	Dissemination and Communication Plan	WP6	4	Document available	31/12/2022	
M3	Advisory Board formed	WP1	6	Members identified	28/02/2023	
M4	Green Portal on line	WP3	6	Portal organised	28/02/2023	
M5	Master launched	WP4	9	Students enrolled	31/05/2023	
M6	First Stakeholder joint initiative	WP2	10	Digital Co-Creation Workshop organised	30/06/2023	
M7	Programmes and training contents ready (first version)	WP5	16	End of testing activities; Programmes and training contents validated	31/12/2023	
M8	Final dissemination event	WP6	36	Conference organised; invitation sent; description in D6.2	31/08/2025	

D1.1: Project Management Plan (PMP) and Data Management Plan (DMP), Version 04.01; 05/08/2025

WBS ID	Task Name	Start	End	Duration	ES	EF	LS	LF	TF	FF	Predecessors
100	100	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	101	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	102	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	103	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	104	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
200	200	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	201	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	202	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	203	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
300	300	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	301	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	302	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
400	400	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	401	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
500	500	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	501	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	502	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	503	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	504	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
600	600	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	601	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	602	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
700	700	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	701	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
800	800	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	801	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	802	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	803	2025-01-01	2025-01-01	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	

11. ANNEX 3: Financial and Resource management

The annex is a working document FILE EXCEL. Each partner has its own file to update; when updated, no need to change the name of the file, unless substantial changes to the file structure are done; the attachment provided is the pdf version

The template used for financial monitoring is indicative and partners may complete it differently or in part, in line with their usual financial monitoring and accounting practices and Horizon Europe rules.

Figure 5: screenshot of the file “Financial and Resource management“

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underling the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and should be qualitatively appropriate in order to train the adequate number of workers, to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES regardless their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, along with the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against lack of information, bad quality material, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

Coordinator: **AZZERO CO2 SRL (AzzeroCO2)**

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